

Buzan Mind Mapping: An Efficient Technique for Note-Taking

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Abstract : Buzan mind mapping is an efficient system of note-taking that makes revision a fun thing to do for students. Tony Buzan has been teaching children all over the world for the past thirty years and has proved that mind maps are the magic formula in the classroom for everyone. The purpose of this paper is to discuss the importance of Buzan mind mapping as a note-taking technique for the secondary school students. This paper also examines the mind mapping technique, advantages and disadvantages of hand-drawn mind maps. Samples of students' mind maps were presented and discussed.

Keywords : Buzan mind mapping, note-taking technique, hand-drawn, mind maps

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